

Cross Border Migrants From Bangladesh in East India

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Abstract

The main aim of the research paper is to critically analyse the problem question “How has migration from what is today Bangladeshi contributed to economic development of the Indian region?” According to author Rizwana Shamshad’s book “Bangladeshi Migrants in India”, the current nationalist undertaking in India can be best understood when studied in totality over the entire previous century, especially in the context of East Bengal or East Pakistan or simply Bengalis who chose to migrate into areas of Eastern parts of India especially West Bengal and Assam. The Indian struggle for independence in its political context since 1885, was aimed at freedom from colonial rule which resulted in laying the foundation of the Indian National Congress (INC). In 1906 Indian Muslim League (IML), made efforts to protect the interests of Muslims who were increasingly threatened being a minority community under the colonial rule of the Britishers. However, with the passage of time, the Indian National Congress adopted a more secular approach by including the Rashtriya Swayam Sevak Sangh (RSS), a more fascist and anti-Muslim body in comparison to the Indian Muslim League (Shamshad, R. 2017).

Keywords

Cross Border Migrants Bangladesh East India

Introduction

Due to lack of agreement over power-sharing between the representatives of the Indian National Congress and the Indian Muslim League, the Indian subcontinent was partitioned on the basis of religion in 1947, which also witnessed bloodshed, violence and migration on a large scale. Bangladesh was created in 1971, after East Pakistan snapped off its ties with West Pakistan ending the two-nation theory, which created complications for the Bengalis due to their ethnicity and language, despite similar religious concerns over which the 1947 partition took place (Shamshad, R. 2017).

Although the Indian constitution follows a secular ideology however, regional and nationalistic sentiments based on ethnicity could not be ruled out which were witnessed in several ethnic nationalist movements post 1947, independent India. This also resulted in communal tensions and the rise of a new form of nationalism more based on Hindutva that chose to ignore or exclude Muslims and other minority religious communities from the Indian Hindu States (Shamshad, R. 2017).

Author Elena Dabova states that, despite several debates of Globalization and serious concerns over security threats and practices, construction of walls across the borders in an attempt to fence and control trans-national border movements of people continues to be an adopted practice by nations that wish to control and protect their security, ethnicity and ecology. The Indian land border is managed by the Border Security Forces (BSF), along with some fencing between India and Bangladesh owing to its largely riverine topography. However, looking at migration trends today from a moral perspective it seems that a large number of people become victims of cruel injustice on account of being born in a particular country and being governed by a particular political party. While it jeopardizes and curbs the freedom of people to choose a better life with options for an honorable livelihood, ambitious and economically strong superpowers continue to look over the rights of people who desire to choose more fulfilling and rewarding opportunities for a better life.

Objective of study

The main aim of the research paper is to critically analyse the problem question “How has migration from what is today Bangladeshi contributed to economic development of the Indian region?”

Review of Literature

Identifying The Problem Elements

Author Rizwana Shamshad in the book states that post 1971, large-scale migration was witnessed from Bangladesh into India especially among the Hindus who became victims of religious persecution and also migrated for economic reasons. Besides, there were migrants from the Muslim community who were mainly driven for financial reasons and more willing to contribute as farmers, laborers, rickshaw pullers or daily wagers who preferred to migrate into the districts that bordered Bangladesh. Besides financial reasons, which usually gets them tagged as economic migrants, the main reason for such large-scale migration from Bangladesh was driven by the need to preserve their ethnicity and language. Overall, the migration of Bengalis from Bangladesh has received mass opposition and hostility especially by the Assamese who view these migrants as foreigners and often raise their voice in protest for deporting them back to Bangladesh. Such issues have been shaping election results, political debates and constantly challenging the Rule of Law (Shamshad, R. 2017).

Over the years, Ethnic Assamese Nationalists have seen the rise of several movements such as the Assam Movement, Assam Gana Parishad (AGP) and United Liberation Front

of Assam (ULFA), as leading political parties that oppose Bengali and Bangladeshi presence considering it as a major demographic, economic, political and security threat in Assam (Shamshad, R. 2017).

Demographic transformation of Assam due to a huge influx of cross border immigrants from Bangladesh has for long been a cause of social differences, unease and increasing security concerns for India. However, despite opposition and condemnation by the local population, the All-India United Democratic Front (AIUDF) and several other local parties have encouraged trans-border migrants to settle into Assam thereby transforming four Hindu dominated districts into a Muslim majority hub. According to independent estimates, approximately 1.5 to 2 million cross border immigrants in Assam belong to the Muslim community which is approximately 25% of the total population in Assam (Singh, R. 2017).

The biggest hurdle faced by the Tribunals Act 1983 is to identify and deport the influx of Bangladeshi migrants, although it is a clearly established fact that migration has been happening on a large scale. Also, the 3 Judge bench of the Supreme Court in 2005, had termed this migration as an aggression which has resulted in creating panic and making the locals insecure in Assam and other North Eastern States. Furthermore, reports indicate that despite not having proper national identification documents, a majority of the cross-border Bangladeshi migrants had their votes registered in Assam (Singh, R. 2017).

Besides, it is alarming to note that Muslim population numbers increased at an unprecedented rate in Assam due to vested interests of certain political parties, which has resulted in at least five Hindu dominated districts registering a sharp decrease in their Hindu populations, while they gradually turned into a Muslim dominated immigrant hub. For instance, in 1951 Goalpara district had approximately 54% Hindus residing in it, whereas in 2011 only 38% Hindus were registered in the census. The next three decades are likely to see a further dip in Hindu population numbers. Comparisons indicate that in 1951 the Muslim population in Goalpara District which was 43% had increased to 56% in 2011, with a likely predicted increase in the coming years if migrants continue crossing the borders into India (Singh, R. 2017).

Main Text

International Law, Norms, Local Laws And Policy

Owing to the non-obligatory nature of International Law and the dominance of domestic Law, most refugees, immigrants, stateless people and undocumented migrants continue to live a life of insecurity and victimization often lacking opportunities for better livelihood and survival making them more vulnerable in their existing challenging circumstances (Ghosh, A. B. 2021).

According to International Norms, refugees upon fleeing seek shelter in other countries especially the neighboring ones fearing persecution based on political, religious, ethnic or other grounds. However, when migrants flee the country of their origin for economic benefits and other employment reasons, such reasons do not find any mention in the definition of Refugee in Refugee Law and in this case cross border migrants from Bangladesh. It is for these reasons that a sound national legislation must be formulated to address these issues (Sharma, C. K. 2012)

The UNHCR in 1994, set up a five-member panel comprising of eminent persons to help South Asian countries in developing Domestic Refugee Laws and the proposed Refugee Laws 1997. Thereafter, the South Asia Declaration on Refugees in 2004 and the introduction of a Private Member Asylum Bill in the Indian parliament by Shashi Tharoor in 2015, helped to enact India's National Refugee Law. The biggest challenge for India was to take into account the interests of its local population along with protecting its national interests. Therefore, India needed to be very alert before accepting in totality all the advice given by the UNHCR panel which was more an opinion of activists who prioritized the rights and privileges of asylum seekers more than the safety and security concerns of India (Acharya, B. 2016).

Assam Accord

The Government of Assam, Union of India, All Assam Gana Sangram Parishad and All Assam Student Union signed the Assam Accord on 15 August 1985, so that the process of implementing the various clauses of the Assam Accord could be carried out. Thereafter an implementation of the Assam Accord Department was set up in 1986. This memorandum of settlement was a movement that was directed at deporting and identifying all foreigners especially cross border immigrants from Bangladesh. Unfortunately there were more than 855 fatalities during the Assam movement (Assam, G. o. 2021).

NRC and Its Relation with The Assam Accord

Under the regulations and recommendations of the Assam Accord and the National Register of Citizens, all those people who migrated between 1951 and 1971, including post partition refugees, would be granted Indian citizenship. However, clause 6 mentions that such citizens would not be able to benefit from the safeguards that were meant for the local people of Assam. The Citizenship Act 1955, under clause 6 permits migrants who are not recognized according to the regulations of the Assam Accord, to continue living in Assam. However, the Citizenship Amendment Act (CAA), according to the AASU, is totally opposed to the purpose and objectives mentioned under Section 6 (a), of the

Citizenship Act 1955. Most Unions and Organizations in Assam consider the CAA to be in disagreement with the Assam Accord of 1985 and also endangering the identity of Assam which is likely to result in unchecked migration from Bangladesh into Assam further threatening its cultural identity (Assam, G. o. 2021).

The Citizenship Act 1955, is a pathway for cross border migrants to acquire citizenship which is mainly directed at helping people who are victims of religious persecution and belonging to certain national and religious communities. For instance, Buddhists, Sikhs, Jains, Hindus, Parsi's and Christian communities who belong to either Pakistan, Afghanistan or Bangladesh could be facilitated through the pathway to acquire Indian Citizenship. An important point to note is that the CAA is not applicable on Assamese Tribal areas and other States of North East India. Assam's demographic threat has been viewed as a challenge to the migration policy and demography of Assam, mainly because Bangladesh was formerly known as East Pakistan (Assam, G. o. 2021).

Origin of The Conflict

By mid-19th century, the British East India Company in its efforts to promote Bengali in the bureaucracy started to make policies that prioritized Bengali language. Furthermore, the creation of East Pakistan prompted the rush of immigrants into Assam's fields and tea estates. However, the present conflict is more focused on the influx of migration in waves that resulted in the 1971 Pakistan War with India. Post Indo-Pakistan War promoted movements that protested for the implementation of stringent Laws. Besides, followers of the All-Assam Student Union started to raise slogans demanding changes in the new policy, enacting a new legislation and also recommending fortification of the border through a wall with Bangladesh. In 1985, after six long years of protest and agitation, Government of India was pressurized by the AASU, which facilitated the signing of the Assam Accord with various organizations in Assam (Assam, G. o. 2021).

Thereafter, the Accord was implemented which legislated that all those people would be deported from Assam who had entered after March 24, 1971. In addition, the Assam Accord also directed the Union to make the international border of Assam more secure. However, this gave rise to a conflict between the Union of India and Assam mainly because it required Assam to update its National Register of Citizens (NRC). At present, only the names of Indian citizens that reside in Assam feature in the NRC list and the excluded persons are either deported or sent into detention centers. In 2013, the Assam Public Works Department requested for an update in the NRC, the Supreme Court directed the Government for updating the list and finally on 31 August 2019, the final controversial list was published in which more than 1900,000 residents were not included as residents, resulting in further clashes and protests. This contested move has resulted in the NRC continuing to be argued and debated in the Supreme Court through different litigations (Assam, G. o. 2021).

Assam's Link With CAA

Muslim Students Federation (MSF), and the AASU strongly fear that the Assamese identity was under a severe threat under the CAA. The CAA adopts a pathway to aid migrants from Bangladesh to acquire citizenship whereas, the NRC would not have included such citizens into the list especially if the persons belonged to the Muslim community. According to the provisions of the Act, all non-Indians that gained entry into India after 25.03.1971, without a valid passport, lawful authorization and travel documents would be allowed to continue living in India besides, also getting the benefits of gaining Indian citizenship. These recommendations were further supported by the MSF and AASU to support the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous People (UNDRIP), upholding their right against the destruction of their culture and forced assimilation. However, there are increasing fears among members of the unions and the federations who feel that the CAA upon being implemented would further change the demography of India. India being a prominent member of the United Nations and also having voted in favor of UNDRIP must make efforts to fulfill the provisions of the declaration by upholding the rights of indigenous people (Assam, G. o. 2021).

Analysis

Analyzing The Research Questions

These developments require a thorough analysis and adoption of an objective approach to understand when and how the local ethnic nationalist groups in Assam started to feel threatened by migrants from Bangladesh, when they themselves had allowed them to work as daily wagers and laborers in their farms and Tea Estates at low wages. Another pertinent question is when the Rashtriya Swayam Sevak Sangh (RSS), joined the Indian National Congress (INC), were they not aware that migrants from Bangladesh belong to both the Hindu and Muslim communities and opposing the presence of one community over another only highlights the Hindutva agenda of the BJP (Shamshad, R. 2017).

Besides, a deeper analysis needs to be undertaken to understand why migration from Bangladesh does not become a political agenda in West Bengal? The answers to these questions are likely to clear the air around the Nationalist Agenda in the State of Eastern parts of India that border Bangladesh and the overall Indian policy towards migrants from Bangladesh. Migration from Bangladesh should not be taken as a singular phenomenon but rather understood in context with its historical, social and ethnic background. Since most Bangladeshi's share an essentially Bengali ethnicity, language, culture and past unity among people from both religious communities representing Muslim and Hindus, it makes the people of West Bengal more affiliated towards migrants from Bangladesh as

compared to the local Assamese who are distinct in language and culture and consider them as outsiders (Shamshad, R. 2017).

Certain strong words such as accepting or rejecting, including or excluding, refugee and infiltrator, terrorist and victim, Hindu and Muslim, economic burden and economic contributor, land cultivator and land grabber, although existing in pairs highlight the mindset of the local communities towards migration from Bangladesh into India and the Indian Nationalist Context. These and the rise of many other local movements have constantly attempted to attack, break down, repress and distance migrants from Bangladesh with a constant refusal to identify and regard them as worthy beings by distorting their image with negative adjectives such as infiltrators, terrorists, insurgents and illegal migrants that labels them with a stigmatic and dehumanizing identity (Shamshad, R. 2017).

It is sad to note that instead of honoring the migrants for their hard work, toil, labor and contribution to nation building, they are rather branded as terrorists, outsiders and more often considered as a threat to the secular status of India. In an endeavor to understand the core tenets of Indian Nationalism, the responses of academicians, political activists, Human Rights activists and Journalists were taken into account to understand the context of Indian Nationalism in an analytical manner especially which revolves around the protection and welfare of migrants from Bangladesh (Shamshad, R. 2017).

A number of Human Rights Organizations have raised their concerns regarding the deportation efforts that were undertaken at a large scale in 1992, which repatriated migrants from Bangladesh. Such an Act is considered an outright one-sided attack on the Muslim community of Bangladesh who have been indirectly blamed for invading the border districts in East India and also for their links with terrorist groups. This Act is highly condemnable and considered highly immoral (Shamshad, R. 2017).

The constructed wall across the India Bangladesh border fails to put a real check on controlling trans-border migration due to its unique geographical location. Moreover it is largely backed with a huge demand to exploit labor from economically and politically challenged Bangladesh which has also encouraged corruption across the border. To add to this, the existence of an unnatural border which is a means of connecting between the two nations, fails to address the needs and its obligations towards International Migrants. This has prompted immense criticism from the international migration regime, who are seriously evaluating the efficacy of walls in checking trans-border migration. Since there are serious differences and political ambitions between India and Pakistan, migration from Bangladesh which was a part of Pakistan prior to 1971, is largely looked at as a threat because it is backed by Pakistan controlled mafias. This gives India an opportunity to cheer, when Muslims willingly leave Bangladesh to work in a secular country. Additionally this has prompted the Indian Government to relook at its policy on citizenship, so that social inequality can be addressed (Mundo, A. 2014).

Migration from Bangladesh continues to remain unchecked into eastern parts of India for several decades. However, the issue of security threats to India, particularly the South Asian Region were highlighted to target a particular community even before the work on border fencing and building the wall was started (Mundo, A. 2014).

International media has always been very selective in highlighting cases of suffering immigrants and the inhumane treatment of cross border migrants who are shot at by the Border security Force guards. This has led to several other cases of discrimination and increasing use of resorting to bribes to influence the BSF guards for crossing the borders. However, not much attention is given to highlight the confrontation that takes place between the ones that wish to cross the border and the border guards or those that are permitted entry because of being allegedly sponsored by a mafia group that organizes exploitation of labor. There is also no mention by the international community about this gross discrimination, inequality and exploitative policy adopted by the Indian Government that openly flaunts India's secular nature of democracy but is encouraging exploitation and oppression of the economically challenged migrant labor force from Bangladesh. There is also another belief that the plight of the Muslim population in India which was primarily indigenous and had no share in the ruling power circles is the reason for them continuing to remain socially and occupationally backward since thousands of years (Mundo, A. 2014).

Result and Discussion

Much of the civil society can organize groups and communities to uphold and preserve the social, cultural, political and economic needs of the citizens in a State. However, by following a more inclusive approach definitely some space can be given to fellow beings from another neighboring country practicing a different religion, but at the same time contributing actively towards the economy of a State and also working as an equal partner in various manual construction and daily wage labor jobs. This is largely in context with the fact that a civil society does not follow or promote any single religious or ethnic group, it only strives to create space for a humane existence for all individuals that are culturally, religiously, politically and differently aligned and deserve an inherently inclusive plural national approach instead of promoting a singular separatist nationalist agenda (Shamshad, R. 2017).

In context with the construction of a wall between Bangladesh and India, a more liberal and an assimilative approach needs to be adopted prioritizing mutual benefit based on universal values of brotherhood instead of being based on narrow, ethnic, cultural, traditional, social and religious differences, which divide communities and also threaten global peace and security (Mundo, A. 2014).

Findings

Human Rights Watch reports that India has deported hundreds of Muslims, many believed to be Indian citizens to Bangladesh without proper legal procedures. The organization highlights due process violations, lack of individualized hearings, and racial profiling. Several deportees reportedly held Indian documents or were born in India. The expulsions are largely linked to the National Register of Citizens (NRC) and Citizenship Amendment Act (CAA) fallout. HRW urges India to halt unlawful deportations and respect international legal standards. India has stepped up deportations of Muslims from Assam and West Bengal to Bangladesh, claiming they are undocumented immigrants (Human Rights Watch, 2025).

Conclusion

The report notes many deportees lack ties to Bangladesh and include Indian citizens. Families have been torn apart, with local protests growing. Critics say the expulsions disproportionately target Muslims, while officials defend them as part of immigration enforcement. The Washington Post highlights growing human rights concerns and regional diplomatic tensions. According to rights groups cited by The Guardian, India is deporting Muslim citizens under the guise of immigration enforcement. Many affected individuals have lived in India for generations and possess official documents (the Washington Post, 2025). Activists argue that the campaign targets Muslims based on ethnicity and religion, with insufficient legal review. Deportations are linked to NRC fallout and rising anti-immigrant rhetoric. Bangladesh has reportedly protested receiving stateless individuals. The report raises alarms about constitutional violations and minority persecution (Guardian, 2025).

According to author Aldea Mundo, constructing physical walls cannot put an end to trans-border migration. It can only serve to diversify the endless possibilities for corruption, smuggling, and multiplication of mafia gangs, increasing exploitation of the helplessness of the migrants, severe violence by the border guards and increasing the prices of smuggled goods. The author has very aptly described wall fencing across the India Bangladesh border as a "Psychological Frenzy" where there is social and economic stability on one side that is wall protected, offering greater opportunities to mafia gangs to expand their presence in the black market (Mundo, A. 2014).

Although the threat of migrants from Bangladesh is overelaborated, a proper policy to regulate the flow of immigration instead of containing it would better address the flaws in the existing migrant policy. Such an endeavor would also get international validation because it would be based on a more transparent and protective support, based on protecting International Human Rights. Garson, an OECD international Migration specialist believes that it is unfeasible to control migration, therefore, wishing for zero migration is only a figment of imagination. Instead, the influx of migrants can be channelized into a more sustainable International Welfare System through liberalization in regulations at the national and international level (Jean-Pierre Garson. 2004). In the case of Bangladesh and India, with their limited natural resources and geographical area, several people in their quest for a more secure future have also been compelled to opt for international immigration to other countries, instead of India (Mundo, A. 2014).

In my opinion, to find solutions to growing economic concerns on a large scale, a multi-pronged approach with a proper legal framework and a well-coordinated strategy is required. Trans border migrations being inevitable, do take place which is also the case with Bangladesh. Since, the Indian economy is growing at a rapid pace, it is the most attractive option for Bangladeshi migrants who wish to earn their livelihood. However, it cannot be ignored that 1/4th of the population in India still continues to live below the poverty line, which will further get a setback if unchecked migration continues. Bangladesh being India's neighboring country, it would be in the best interest of India not to leave behind Bangladesh while it is struggling with economic growth. India can jointly collaborate with Bangladesh to start development programs that benefit people across both sides of the border. Such development programs are best undertaken by NGOs that help to upgrade healthcare and basic education facilities while also providing local employment.

Suggestions for the future Study

To enable safety of immigrants back into their country of origin, a proper mechanism of dialogue between the two affected countries needs to be established so that the process of verification of identity and nationality of immigrants can be carried out smoothly. This step will also help to support the already initiated national identity card program called Aadhar card program in India. It is only through cooperation that bilateral relations between India and other countries from where immigrants had gained entry into India can be maintained. Honest sharing of information can help to uphold the trust related to cross-border migration between two States so that peace, stability, Human Rights issues and displacement of people can be addressed (Ghosh, A. B. 2021).

Efforts of NGO's especially in the case of India and Bangladesh could be utilized to verify and register immigrants and uphold trust building efforts to resettle stateless, overstaying and cross-border migrants (Ghosh, A. B. 2021).

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